

NPAR TESTS

/MANN-WHITNEY = SmlArena BY Group (1.00,2.00)

Ranks

		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
SmlArena	Beacon	5	11.00	55.00
	Random	15	10.33	155.00
	Total	20		

Test Statistics

	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
SmlArena	35.00	155.00	-.22	.827

NPAR TESTS

/MANN-WHITNEY = MedArena BY Group (1.00,2.00)

Ranks

		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
MedArena	Beacon	5	9.80	49.00
	Random	15	10.73	161.00
	Total	20		

Test Statistics

	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
MedArena	34.00	49.00	-.31	.760

NPAR TESTS

/MANN-WHITNEY = LrgArena BY Group (1.00,2.00)

Ranks

		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
LrgArena	Beacon	5	9.00	45.00
	Random	15	11.00	165.00
	Total	20		

Test Statistics

	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
LrgArena	30.00	45.00	-.65	.513